

THE IMPORTANCE OF DEVELOPING STUDENTS' INTERCULTURAL COMPETENCE IN ELT

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Abstract: In modern sociocultural conditions, problems of linguistic communication become particularly relevant and economic globalization, cultural and educational integration have contributed to increased attention to English as the language of intercultural communication. Research shows that achieving higher levels of language proficiency depends on thinking like a target language speaker and such thinking requires cultural understanding. An intercultural speaker needs to possess knowledge and awareness of cultures, open-mindedness, and a set of skills, which will allow her/him to avoid misunderstandings in the target language. Thus, how is the EFL learner supposed to develop intercultural competence? This article highlights the importance of developing intercultural competence in ELT.

Key words: culture, skills, cultural knowledge, intercultural competence, intercultural communication, intercultural awareness, attitude, cultural environment.

Nowadays, when different peoples, languages, and cultures are getting closer to each other, it is one of the urgent issues to be interested in other cultures, to respect them, to try to understand them, and to learn to approach them with patience. It is precisely because of this that the issues of intercultural and international communication have attracted general attention.

Strategies for developing intercultural communication competence have become a major area for current research. Many language teacher researchers emphasize the importance of intercultural understanding, cultural awareness, and the development of specific skills and attitudes. The key to successful language learning is the ability to understand and communicate in a different cultural environment. Intercultural competence is a person's ability to effectively and adequately interact with representatives of other cultures, to know and understand culture, communication and interaction methods, as well as the ability to adapt to new conditions and situations. Therefore, it is important to develop students' intercultural competence in a multinational and multilingual society and to prepare them for communication with representatives of different countries and cultures.

The relationship between language and culture, as well as the role of cultural competence in communicative competence has come increasingly under many studies. Research shows that achieving higher levels of language proficiency depends on thinking like a target language speaker and such thinking requires cultural understanding. Extra-linguistic elements such as values, beliefs, norms, rituals, and traditions are also key components of communication exchanges, which should be taught target culture interactively in foreign language classrooms in order to enhance intercultural competence.

Analysis of several works of foreign and domestic researchers, traditionally intercultural competence consists of three components:

- Knowledge;
- Attitude;
- Skills.

Knowledge includes linguistic and cultural information, as well as information about the process of interaction between cultures.

Attitude determines a person's desire and thoughts to communicate with people from other cultures.

Skills allow the correct use of knowledge and attitudes in practice in the process of intercultural communication.

The most famous structural model of intercultural competence in foreign language teaching methodology is M. Bayram's model. According to Bayram (1997), intercultural competence has the status of independent competence in connection with foreign language communicative competence, and its successful formation in a foreign language learner is important for intercultural communication, because in the process of communicating in a foreign language, the learner does not simply become a communicative partner. "Approaching the level of general cultural competence of a native speaker is not possible, and not necessary, because of cultural differences. What the student really needs is to be a mediator between representatives of different cultures, a full participant in the communication of cultures" (Byram, 1997).

Bayram (1997) determines that the following components are important in the structure of intercultural competence:

-to have knowledge of all components of the culture of their own country and the culture of their partner in intercultural communication, as well as knowledge of their interactions at the individual and social level;

- perception of various phenomena and events of the culture of the foreign language and identification of possible "zones" of misunderstandings or potential conflicts (intercultural acceptance skills);

- interpretation of foreign language culture in a culturally diverse and culturally similar language environment, ownership of stereotypes of interest accepted in the studied culture; resolving misunderstandings, working as a cultural mediator (effective intercultural skills);

- access to intercultural communication;

- the ability to establish correct, open and interesting relationships with each other;

- the desire and desire to fight with cultural shortcomings and illusions.

Thus, according to this model, a person with intercultural competence distinguishes the following characteristics: the ability to see the relations of different cultures (both external and internal to society); the ability to mediate, to interpret one culture in terms of another culture; Critical and analytical understanding of own and other cultures; refers to his personal worldview and culturally specific thinking.

The main advantage of M. Bayram's model is that there are a number of skills that allow learners to communicate with people of different cultures, regardless of the difference in the language of communication.

Analyzing Bayram's model of intercultural competence shows us that the knowledge, skills and attitudes that the language learners need to have differ from each other and aim at achieving one goal which is to prepare them for full intercultural communication.

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